

From individual to joint species distribution models: a comparison of model complexity and predictive performance

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Importance of Explanatory Variables by Taxon in the Hierarchical Multi-Species Model

The following plots compare the calibrated probabilities of occurrence and the explanatory variables for all taxa in the hierarchical multi-species distribution model UF0. The calibrated probabilities of occurrence (based on the marginal posterior taxon-specific parameter distributions β_{kj}^{taxa}) produce strong positive or negative responses for explanatory variables with a good explanatory power. Taxa are ordered by decreasing number of occurrences and show a variety of distinct response curves for the selected explanatory variables.

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Chironomidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Limoniidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Simuliidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Oligochaeta

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Baetis_alpinus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Empididae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Baetis_rhodani*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Ceratopogonidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Psychodidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Elmidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Isoperla*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Planariidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Baetis_muticus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Gammaridae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Athericidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Prostigmata

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhyacophila_tristis*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Hydraenidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Protonemura_lateralis*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Nemoura_mortoni*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Nematoda

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Sericostoma*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Scirtidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Habroleptoides_confusa*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Blephariceridae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Ecdyonurus_helveticus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Brachyptera_risi*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Sphaeriidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Dixidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Amphinemura*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Odontocerus_albicorne*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Dictyogenus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Tinodes*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Tipulidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Plectrocnemia

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Nemoura_minima*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Drusus_discolor*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_loyolaea*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Epeorus_alpicola*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Leuctra_braueri*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Epeorus_assimilis*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Stratiomyidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Philopotamus_ludificatus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Habrophlebia_lauta*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Dugesiidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Centroptilum_luteolum*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Ecdyonurus_venosus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_puthzi*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Chloroperla_susemicheli*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Paraleptophlebia_submarginata*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Ecdyonurus picteti*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Baetis_lutheri*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Dytiscidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Thaumaleidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhyacophila_hirticornis*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_alpestris*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Capnioneura_nemuroides*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Protonemura_brevistyla*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Ephemera_danica*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_picteti*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Habroleptoides_auberti*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Metanoea*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Siphonoperla_torrentium*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Glossosoma*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Leuctra_nigra*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Lymnaeidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Hydropsyche_siltalai*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Electrogena_ujhelyii*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhabdiopteryx*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Perلودes*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Erpobdellidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Protonemura_intricata*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Perla_grandis*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Wormaldia*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Asellidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Cryptothrix_nebulicola*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Protonemura_nimborum*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Sialidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Ptychopteridae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Hydrophilidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Ecdyonurus_alpinus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Glossiphoniidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Drusus_annulatus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Cordulegastridae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Siphonoperla_montana*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Ephemerella_mucronata*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Serratella ignita*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_hybrida*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_nivata*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Anthomyiidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Leuctra_major*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Lype

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Hydroptilidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Drusus_biguttatus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Ecdyonurus_torrentis*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_degrangei*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Perla marginata*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Nemurella_pictetii*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Ancylus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Tabanidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Polycentropus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Potamophylax_cingulatus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Drusus_melanchaetes*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena semicolorata*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_dorieri*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Hydrobiidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Goeridae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Gyrinidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Calopterygidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Dinocras*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Lepidostomatidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Brachyptera_seticornis*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_gratianopolitana*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_grischuna*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Ecclisopteryx madida*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Rhagionidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Physidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhyacophila_praemorsa*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Melampophylax_mucoreus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Baetis_venus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Niphargidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Chloroperla_tripunctata*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Nemoura_marginata*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Agapetus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Torleya_major*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Drusus nigrescens*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhyacophila_intermedia*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Nemoura_flexuosa*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Drusus_muelleri*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Hydropsyche_tenuis*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Electrogena_lateralis*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Capnia*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Haliplidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Dolichopodidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Micrasema_morosum*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Psychomyia_pusilla*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Caenis_macrura*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Hydropsyche_instabilis*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Syrphidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Siphonurus_lacustris*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhyacophila_stigmatica*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Protonemura_praecox*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Corixidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Planorbidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Leuctra_schmidei*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Baetis vardarensis*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Baetis_bucерatus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Scathophagidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhyacophila_pubescens*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Allogamus_auricollis*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhyacophila_torrentium*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Mystacides*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Coenagrionidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Dryopidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Synagapetus_dubitans*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Leuctra_rosinae*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Catagapetus_nigrans*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Astacidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Osmyliidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Piscicolidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Dendrocoelidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Baetis_melanonyx*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Glyptotaelius_pellucidus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Psephenidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Gerridae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Protonemura_meyeri*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_landai*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Philopotamus_variegatus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Synagapetus iridipennis*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Halesus_radiatus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhyacophila_fasciata*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Drusus_monticola*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Lepidoptera

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Veliidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Drusus_alpinus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Ernodes

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Platycnemididae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Cnidaria

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Athripsodes

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Caenis_rivulorum*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Anobolia*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Leuctra_inermis*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_allobrogica*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Ptilocolepus_granulatus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Cloeon_dipterum*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Baetis_nexus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Caenis_horaria*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Hydropsyche_dinarica*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Protonemura_nimborella*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Bithyniidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Valvatidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Aphelocheiridae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Chaetopteryx_major*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Ecclisopteryx_guttulata*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Baetis_niger*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Leuctra_hippopus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Nemoura_cambrica*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Mesoveliidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Holocentropus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Besdolus_imhoffi*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Protonemura_auberti*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhyacophila_simulatrix*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Hydropsyche_saxonica*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhyacophila_dorsalis*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Diplectrona atra*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Chaoboridae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Consortophylax consors*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Habrophlebia_eldae*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Limnephilus_lunatus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Notidobia_ciliaris*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Baetis liebenaueae*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Gomphidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Baetis_nubecularis*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Oecetis_testacea*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Caenis_luctuosa*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Hymenoptera

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Beraea_pullata*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Micrasema_setiferum*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Cheumatopsyche_lepida*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Ceraclea_annulicornis*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Nemoura_cinerea*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Drusus_mixtus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Agrypnia*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Habrophlebia_fusca*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Hydropsyche_pellucidula*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Sciomyzidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Ephydriidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Halesus_rubricollis*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Leuctra_rauscheri*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Beraea_maurus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Curculionidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Notonectidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhyacophila_glareosa*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Leuctra_pseudosignifera*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Potamanthus_luteus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Heptagenia sulphurea*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Micropterna_nycterobia*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Ceraclea_dissimilis*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Chrysomelidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_carpatoalpina*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Leuctra_armata*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Culicidae

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Drusus_chrysotus*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for *Rhyacophila_rectispina*

Probability of occurrence (based on the maximum marginal posterior distribution of the taxon-specific parameter) vs explanatory variables for Acroloxiidae

